

Research article

Ultrasonography (USG) Evaluation of Ectopic Pregnancy

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Abstract:

Background The term Ectopic is derived from the Greek word “ektopos” the literal meaning of it is “out of place”. Ectopic Pregnancy is termed as implantation done outside of the uterine cavity. The classification of ectopic pregnancy comprises of tubal as well as non-tubal types¹. The prevalence of EPs tubal is observed to be 95%, and only 5% comprise of the non-tubal type of ectopic pregnancy across the globe.

Aim To study the role of ultrasonography(USG) in the diagnosis of ectopic pregnancy with clinical analysis

Methods One hundred patients with a provisional diagnosis of ectopic pregnancy were studied. Physical examination, urine pregnancy test, transabdominal scan using 5 MHz transducer or transvaginal ultrasonography of 7 MHz was done.

Results The most common cause was tubectomy (20 cases). In post tubal sterilization procedures, most of them were following abdominal tubectomy (12 cases). In this study, all cases of ectopic pregnancy were following 3 years of sterilization. On examination, 45 % of cases presented with pallor and 12 % of cases with shock.

Conclusion Ectopic Pregnancy is observed to be the consequence of obstetric emergency associated with long term mortality and morbidity. Thus, a high degree of suspension deals with diagnosis and treatment that improves the future with reproductive capabilities.

Key words Ectopic, pregnancy, ultrasonography.

INTRODUCTION

The term Ectopic is derived from the Greek word “ektopos” the literal meaning of it is “out of place”. Ectopic Pregnancy is termed as implantation done outside of the uterine cavity. The classification of ectopic pregnancy comprises of tubal as well as non-tubal types^[1]. The prevalence of EPs tubal is observed to be 95%, and only 5% comprise of the non-tubal type of ectopic pregnancy across the globe. These types are associated with the EPS morbidity and mortality ratio as well. Non-tubal EPs do occur in the uterine interstitium region with angular or cornual positions that are related with the cervix, previous caesarean section scar and ovary condition^[2].

In general, it can be said as when a patient is presented with the symptoms of ectopic pregnancy or with other hormonal assays indicating an abnormal pregnancy it is subject to

perform USG to determine the exact location of an intra or extra-uterine pregnancy. The transvaginal US is subjected to be the relevant method for evaluation^[3]. The transvaginal US should be capable of determining the gestational sac when the β -hCG level is observed to be greater than 2000 mIU/mL. The use of transabdominal USG can prove useful in determining the intrauterine pregnancy with β -hCG level reaching 6500mIU/mL^[4].

Ectopic pregnancy is the most common cause of pregnancy that is associated with mortality. Pelvic Ultra-Sonography is done to get assured of the actual status and condition of pregnancy that it is treatable, complicated, and complex and to what level and what are the necessary actions and decisions associated with it^[5]. In other words, ectopic pregnancy can be termed as a condition when a blastocyst is implanted in an abnormal form outside the endometrium of the uterus. US findings are subjected on the basis of the location of pregnancy such as tubal pregnancy, interstitial pregnancy, Cornual pregnancy, Ovarian pregnancy, cervical pregnancy, intraabdominal pregnancy, and heterotopic pregnancy^[6].(Figure 1)

Fig. 1 Ectopic Pregnancy locations.

Interstitial pregnancy. (a) Transvaginal US image obtained along an oblique axis shows the yolk sac (arrowhead) within a gestational sac, which is located in the interstitial portion of the fallopian tube. The interstitial line sign (arrow) is also seen. (b) Diagram of the interstitial pregnancy and the interstitial line sign. (c) Transverse grey-scale US image of the uterus in another patient shows a gestational sac (arrow), which contains an embryo (arrowhead), in the cornua/interstitial portion of the fallopian tube^[7].

The fallopian tube is the most common location found in an ectopic pregnancy. The findings may be seen specifically with substantial improvements seen. Improvement in the diagnostic accuracy handles the abnormal β -hCG level with progesterone level with ectopic pregnancy. Ectopic pregnancy can be detected with the help of a blood test done for hCG as well as with the help of ultrasound scanning done^[8]. Thus, the present research aims to the role of ultrasonography in the diagnosis of ectopic pregnancy with clinical analysis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

One hundred patients with a provisional diagnosis of ectopic pregnancy were studied. Physical examination, urine pregnancy test, transabdominal scan using 5 MHz transducer or transvaginal ultrasonography of 7 MHz was done. The diagnosis of ectopic pregnancy was confirmed by direct observation by laparotomy or laparoscopy (which was taken as the gold standard).

INCLUSION CRITERIA

All patients suspected of having ectopic pregnancy by history and clinical examination and ultrasonography were included.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Intrauterine gestation and Ectopic pregnancy managed by an expectant or medical line of treatment were excluded.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

One hundred patients with a provisional diagnosis of ectopic pregnancy were studied. Clinical examination, urine pregnancy test, transabdominal or transvaginal ultrasonography was done. The diagnosis of ectopic pregnancy was confirmed by direct observation by laparotomy/laparoscopy, which was taken as the gold standard. The different surgical methods of treatment were noted, and post-operative follow-up was done.

RESULTS

During the study period from 06/02/2107 to 06/02/2019, 100 patients were suspected of ectopic pregnancy. The peak age of incidence was 26 to 30 years (34%) followed by patients in the age group of 21–25 (18%). 16 % of patients were above 30 years and 22 % below 22 years. 2nd gravida were the most sufferers (28%). Primi and 3rd gravida was 14 and 10 %, respectively. Least incidence was found in 4th, and above (9 %) of the cases had married life <10 years. 90 % of cases were referred with 48 % belonging to lower socioeconomic status. One or more risk factors were identified in 48 patients (56%). The most common cause being post tubectomy (20 cases). In post tubal sterilization procedures, most of them were following abdominal tubectomy (12 cases). In this study, all cases of ectopic pregnancy were following 3 years of sterilization. 3 cases were with consecutive ectopic pregnancy. Among 7 cases following IUCD, 4 had previous LSCS. In infertile patients, secondary infertility was common (13 cases) compared to primary infertility (Table 1).

Table 1 Distribution of cases by risk.

Risk Factors	No of Cases	%
Tubectomy	20	20
Tuboplasty	12	12
H/O prev ectopic pregnancy	7	7
Intrauterine contraceptive device	7	7
Infertility	19	19
History suggestive of PID	7	7
Previous LSCS	13	13
H/O abortion	5	5
Conceived after ovulation induction	3	3
No identifiable risk factors	7	7

Some patients had more than one risk factor. Most of the cases in our study presented with acute symptoms (44 %) and 35 of them had hemoperitoneum more than 1000 ml. Twelve cases presented with shock. The most common presentation was pain abdomen, followed by amenorrhea and bleeding per vaginum. On examination, 45 % of cases presented with pallor and 12 % of cases with shock. The most common clinical finding was abdominal tenderness and cervical motion tenderness (Table 2). At an approx 60 % of the cases had positive culdocentesis suggesting blood in the pelvic cavity. All the 100 cases had a urine pregnancy test positive.

Table 2 Clinical presentation analysis.

Symptoms	No of Cases	%
Pain in the abdomen	85	85
Amenorrhea	76	76
Bleeding PV	62	62
Vomiting/nausea	20	20
Fever	7	7
Fainting Attacks	4	4
Signs		
Pallor	45	45
Hypertension and shock	12	12
Abdominal tenderness	80	80
Guarding	12	12
Distension	26	26
Cervical motion tenderness	81	81
Fornical tenderness	71	71
Mass in the fornix	31	31

Table 3 Ultrasonographic findings for 50 cases.

Ultrasonographic Findings	No of Cases	%
Complex mass in adnexa (mixed echogenicity)	50	50
Cardiac activity in the adnexa	15	15
Gestational sac in the adnexa	7	7
Hemoperitoneum	40	40
Intrauterine pseudogestational sac	17	17

Most common ultrasonography findings were complex mass in the adnexa in 50 % of the cases; the complex adnexal mass was present with hemoperitoneum. In 8 cases, the adnexal mass was on the opposite side, as confirmed by laparotomy (Table 3). In all the 100 cases studied, ultrasonography provided the definitive diagnosis resulting in 100 % sensitivity and specificity. Predictive value of a positive test was stable at 100 %. In 8 cases, the previous scan done 15 days prior had shown complete abortion with no evidence of extrauterine pregnancy. As the symptoms persisted, the repeat scan showed hemoperitoneum with an adnexal mass.

DISCUSSION

The incidence of the ectopic pregnancy in the study was noticed to be 1 in 140 cases which can be contrasted well with other studies of Majhi et al. (1 in 162)^[5] and Arora et al. (1 in 160)^[3] of ectopic pregnancy. The peak age of incidence noticed as per the results was 26-30 years of age was 34%, it is seen to be consistent with the other results found in contrasting studies being performed by Arora et al.^[3]. In the other contrasting studies most commonly found cases were of tubal pregnancy as well as of salpingectomy as the treatment chosen suitable for patients at a major level (82%), which can be contrasted well with the findings of other studies^[8].

Ultrasonography can be used as the most common technique or procedure to study the findings and detect the complex adnexal mass (60%) with our findings at (50%). As per the results of our study, the majority of the patients showed Complex mass in adnexa (mixed echogenicity) that is 50% and Hemoperitoneum 40% at a major incidence. It was evident from our study and as per referring other studies such as of Levine (2007)^[6] and Seeber (2006)^[9] that the

sensitivity, as well as the specificity, was 100% in the diagnosis as well as treatment of ectopic pregnancy cases by using the procedure of ultrasonography proving helpful and beneficial in finding the exact cause of occurrence and treating the patient with efficacy and control measures^[10].

CONCLUSION

Ectopic Pregnancy is observed to be the consequence of obstetric emergency associated with long term mortality and morbidity. Thus, a high degree of suspension deals with diagnosis and treatment that improves the future with reproductive capabilities. Ultrasonography assists in diagnosis done at an early stage with problems such as early pregnancy and undergoes certain ultrasonography for clear traces to be found with viability and locative sites of pregnancy. It can be termed as the standard diagnosis technique among the available ones, which is used frequently and is suitable for treating ectopic pregnancy. The standardised treatment used for treating ectopic pregnancy with non-invasive and diagnostic tests suggested for treating the ectopic pregnancy with accurate results and diagnosis.

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